

**A SURVEY STUDY FOR SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL SERVICES
DELIVERED TO THE INDIVIDUALS WITH DISABILITIES AT
SPECIAL EDUCATION INSTITUTES AND CENTERS
IN KINGDOM OF JORDAN**

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Abstract:

This recent study has aimed at identifying the special educational services available in Jordan governorate during the period between 2015 and 2016. The study involved data collection related to the services available in 294 special education centers in all Jordan governorates which are divided in 14 provinces areas. To achieve the purpose of this study a special tool was built by the researcher and a group of experts in order to judge the answer of individuals from different specialized areas in the field of special education in Jordan Kingdom. Data were obtained from the web site of the Higher Council for Individual with Disabilities in Jordan (HCD, 2016); also, a group of students in my college had interviewed the principals of these special education institutions. Data were analyzed by using SPSS (Version 21). Results indicated that some severe physical therapy is present in all governorates but speech and language therapy is not available in Al tafeelah governorate. However support service and integration is present in all governorates except Madaba governorate. Finally, the study confirms that there is a shortage in special education in most of the Jordanian governorates. Furthermore, this type of service is needed to be studied in details. This study is not enough. The type of all program included in the service should be yet explored and evaluated. Results indicated that there was significant correlation between disability and the service available in Balqa, Amman which means that the services provided meet the needs of the disability of Population ($P < 0.05$). Also, results indicate that there

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was correlation between governorate and institutionalization. Though, Amman governorate provides the highest level of institutionalization services. And there was marginal significant correlation between the governorate and the early intervention services ($p = 0.058$). Also, there was significant correlation between governorate and physiotherapy services. Though, Amman has the highest indicators. Support service was significant in Amman, Irbid, Zarqa, Mafraq, Balqa. In general, there was a significant correlation between service provided by special education centers and the type of disability.

Keywords: special education service, disability, Jordan

1. Introduction

In the late of the 19th century, special education services have been started in Jordan by the local churches at that time. It was clear that these services were mainly focused on people who were visually impairment and deaf. Those who had disabilities which were obviously physical instead of related to learning (Hadidi, 1998).

This can be attributed to increment of population, and also to the injuries of civil war and other disasters (Turmusani, 1999). However, Hadidi (1998) explained that the report excluded many cases of disabilities like behavior disorders and learning disabilities. This goes back to main reasons, which were because numerous parents abstained on given exact information on the one hand and on the other, there was a lack of reference make to particular categories.

In 1979, the first national survey of exceptional children was conducted in Jordan. Over 18,000 people with disabilities were determined, and in 1996, this number increased up to 55,000. The most predominant classes were physical disability and hearing impairments, 60%, 19% respectively (Hadidi, 1998 A & Dos, 2008)

Ilar Vein, Turmusani (1999) emphasized that predominantly these surveys comprised open-ended questions and socio-cultural values played part in defining disability in the answers by individuals of family. In fact, cultural values played a part in defining disability because they do not want to be associated with the stigma of disabilities. As a result, families of the disabled were overwhelmed with the feeling of shame. Hence, most Jordanian families did not report disabilities fearing scrutiny and shame which in return affects the accuracy of the disability number.

According to Jordanian statistics, the number of people who were determined to have disabilities amounted to 62,986 in 2004 (Al Zyoud, 2011). However considerable doubt still existed in distinguishing disabilities in young children, such as, there were 8-

12% of children in regular schools who having learning disabilities (LD). Later, discovered information such this, was not considered after the last survey so the statistics are still vague (UNICEF, 2007). In the late of 1970s, many efforts were taken towards exploration and improvement of special education services. University of Jordan was paying attention to especial education needs through focusing especially on measurement and assessment of children with disabilities. In 1996, the University of Jordan graduated the first regiment of special education teachers. In the 1980s and 1990s the Jordanian researchers developed a version of Standard ford Benet Intelligence Scale (IQ) For Jordanian environment (Al Rosan, 1996). At the same time, lots of tests were developed in order to evaluate and measure children's abilities with general and specific learning disabilities (Alrosan, 1996). Because of this attention, an increasing amount of individuals with special needs has enforced the government to build interest in educating them in public school. However, under the Jordanian constitution everyone has the right to free public education. Educational policies in Jordan were obligated to focus on the necessities of basic and comprehensive service for students with learning disabilities.

In the late 1960s, primary services toward disabled individuals in Jordan began. At the same time, the individuals who are deaf, blind and intellectual disabled started to receive services through the establishment of the first institution (Zainudin, 2013). In 1979, the government instituted the first initiative founded by the ministry of social development (MSD, 2005) in order to be accountable for providing educational, vocational rehabilitation and other services through organizations, schools and special classes under its supervision. In addition to this implementing rehabilitation engagement programs and deliver burden-free amenities and tax exemption for the disabled persons and the institutions which provide services to them (MSD, 2005).

In 1993, a law for the Well-being of Disabled people was approved and passed. The law stated the viewpoint of government of Jordan for the treatment of students with disabilities. (MOE, 2009 the law stem for Arabic values, the constitution, the law of human rights and the international act). Consequently, the Ministry of Education (MOE, 2009) founded a department of special education services in order to satisfy the needs of the students with learning disabilities and incorporate students with special needs within the regular classroom and develop the competencies of the teachers in resource room (RR) (Al-Natour et al. 2008).

The Ministry Of Education, additionally, in 1994 the remedial Department was founded by ministry of education (MOE, 2012) which is accountable for special education training. In 2000, the Ministry Of Education established a diagnosis unit for gifted students which ended to establish an excellency school in each province area for

the talent students (Abu-Humour & Alhmouz, 2014). Moreover, the Ministry Of Education established departments which offer inclusive services for the students with special needs (Unisco/WDE/Jordan 2006/2007). Upon the previous background, this cross-sectional study will explore the reality of services delivered to the disabled children.

2. Aim of the study

The study aim to investigate the reality of special education services in Jordan. To achieve the aim of this paper, the following questions were thrown:

1. What are the services available in Jordanian special education institutions?
2. Do the services meet the need of the individuals with disabilities?
3. What is the relationship between the type of the service deliver and the governorate?
4. What is the relation between the service available and the disability?

3. Definition of terms

A. Special educational services: (operational definition):

For the purpose of this study, special education services include any act related to the following services, diagnosing, teaching, learning& instruction, vocational rehabilitation, institutionalization, training courses, physical therapy, physiotherapy, speech and language pathology, early intervention, transportation, and integration.

B. Jordan is an Arab kingdom in Western Asia, on the East Bank of the Jordan River. It is bordered by Saudi Arabia to the east and south, IRAQ to the north-east, Syria to the north, [Palestine](#) and the [Dead Sea](#) to the west and the [Red Sea](#) in its extreme south-west. Jordan is strategically located at the crossroads of Asia, Africa and Europe. The capital, Amman, is Jordan's most populous city as well as the country's economic, political and cultural centre.

Jordan is a relatively small semi-arid almost landlocked country with a population numbering at 9.5 million. [Sunni Islam](#), practiced by around 92% of the population, is the dominant religion in Jordan. It coexists with an indigenous [Christian minority](#). Jordan is considered to be among the safest of [Arab](#) countries in the Middle East, and has avoided long-term terrorism and instability. In the midst of surrounding turmoil, it has been greatly hospitable, accepting refugees from almost all surrounding conflicts as early as 1948, with most notably the estimated 2.1 million [Palestinians](#) and the 1.4 million [Syrian refugees](#) residing in the country. The kingdom is also a refuge to

thousands of [Iraqi Christians](#) fleeing the [Islamic State](#). While Jordan continues to accept refugees, the recent large influx from Syria placed substantial strain on national resources and infrastructure. Jordan is classified as a country of "high human development" with an "upper middle income" economy.

C. Disability: The ADA defines a person with a disability as a person who has a physical or mental impairment that substantially limits one or more major life activity (Alzyoud, 2011). This includes people who have a record of such impairment, even if they do not currently have a disability. It also includes individuals who do not have a disability, but are regarded as having a disability (CEC, 2014). The ADA also makes it unlawful to discriminate against a person based on that person's association with a person with a disability.

4. Methodology

4.1 Research Tool

A special form was developed by the researcher. It consists of eleven dimensions of services which include the following services that delivered to the individuals with disability: institutionalization, diagnosing, rehabilitation, speech-language, physiotherapy, physical therapy, Integration, early intervention, transportation, courses, and teaching services. The name of governorate and type of disability was included in the research instrument.

4.2 Data collection

Permission form was signed from all institutions in Jordan. Also, a letter for co-operation was obtained from the Jordanian Higher Council for Persons with Disabilities (HCPD). Data were obtained from the documentations presented in the Higher Council of persons with Disability web site (HCPD, 2017). 298 institutions deliver special education services in 14 province areas in Jordan (HCPD, 2017).

4.3 Data analysis

Statistical procedures were used to analyze the data (Spss version 21) was used for this purpose, correlation factors (Phi) and frequencies and percentage, and significance (P) and Rho were calculated.

5. Results

This section presents the results of data obtained about the services delivered to the individuals with disabilities in Jordan province areas.

Analyzing the frequencies of services delivered to individuals with disabilities in Jordan indicated some severe variations among governorates. Amman governorate has the highest rank for all services available that is, because it is the capital and has high number of people with special needs (Al Jabery, M., & Zumberg, M. 2008). In the other governorates, there was a shortage in some services. So, in Ajloun, Al Tafela, Jarash and Madaba there were no services related to diagnosis. Teaching and rehabilitation are available in all the governorates. Institutionalization is not present in most of governorates (Ajloun, Al mufraq, Irbid, Madab. However, in Albalqa, Jarash, Karak institutionalization is rarely present.

Physical therapy is present in all governorates but speech, language is not present in Al tafeelah governorate. Support service, and integration is present in all the governorates except Madaba governorate.

Finally, the study confirms that there is a shortage in special education services in most of the Jordanian governorates. Furthermore, the type of service is needed to be studied in details. This study is not enough. The type all program included in the service should be explored and evaluated.

Results indicate that there was significant correlation between disability and the service available in Balqa, Amman which means that the service provided meets the needs of the disability of population ($p < 0.05$).

The results indicate that there was correlation between governorates and institutionalization. Though, Amman governorate provides the highest level of institutionalization services. And there was marginal significant correlation between the governorate and the early intervention services ($p = 0.005$), Also there was significant correlation between governorate and physiotherapy services. Though, Amman has the highest indicators. Support service was significant in Amman, Irbid, Zarqa, Mafraq, Balqa.

In general, there was a significant correlation between services provided by special education centers.

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Table 1

Service	No/ Yes	Governorates <i>n</i> (%)											
		Amman	Ajloon	Albalqa	Al Mafrq	Al tafela	Aqaba	Irbid	Jarash	Karak	Ma'an	Madaba	Zarka
Diagnosis	No	74 (79.6)	5 (100)	11 (78.6)	17 (100)	4 (100)	6 (85.2)	41 (93.4)	5 (100)	15 (88.2)	7 (87.5)	9 (100)	28 (87.5)
	Yes	19 (20.4)	0 (0.0)	3 (21.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (14.3)	3 (6.6)	0 (0.0)	2 (11.8)	1 (12.5)	0 (0.0)	4 (12.5)
Teaching	No	24 (26.1)	2 (40.0)	2 (14.3)	5 (29.4)	1 (25.0)	3 (42.9)	13 (29.5)	4 (80.0)	6 (35.3)	1 (12.5)	4 (44.4)	13 (40.6)
	Yes	68 (73.9)	3 (60.0)	12 (85.7)	12 (85.7)	3 (75.0)	4 (57.1)	31 (70.5)	1 (20.0)	11 (64.7)	7 (87.5)	5 (56.6)	19 (59.4)
Rehabilitation	No	47 (51.1)	2 (40.0)	5 (35.7)	11 (64.7)	3 (75.0)	5 (71.4)	23 (52.3)	0 (0.0)	9 (52.9)	3 (37.5)	4 (44.4)	17 (53.1)
	Yes	45 (48.9)	3 (60.0)	9 (64.3)	6 (35.3)	1 (25.0)	2 (26.6)	21 (47.7)	5 (100.)	8 (47.1)	5 (62.5)	5 (55.6)	15 (46.9)
Institutionalization	No	69 (75.0)	5 (100.)	11 (78.6)	17 (100)	4 (100.)	7 (100)	44 (100)	4 (80,0)	16 (94.1)	8 (100)	9 (100)	29 (90.6)
	Yes	23 (25.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (21.4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	1 (20)	1 (5.9)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	3 (9.4)
Courses	No	30 (32.6)	2 (40.0)	7 (50.0)	8 (47.1)	2 (50.0)	3 (42,9)	11. (25.0)	1 (20.0)	6 (35.3)	4 (50.0)	3 (33,3)	13 (40.6)
	Yes	62 (67.4)	3 (60.0)	7 (50.0)	9 (52.9)	2 (50.0)	4 (57.1)	33 (75.0)	4 (80.0)	11 (64.7)	4 (50.0)	6 (66.7)	19 (59.4)
Physical therapy	No	43 (46.7)	1 (20.0)	7 (50.0)	10 (58.8)	2 (50.0)	4 (57.1)	25 (56.8)	2 (40.0)	7 (41.2)	3 (37.5)	6 (66.7)	16 (50.0)
	Yes	49 (63.3)	4 (80.0)	7 (50.0)	7 (41.2)	2 (50.0)	3 (42.9)	19 (43.2)	3 (60.0)	10 (58.8)	5 (62.5)	3 (33.3)	16 (50.0)
Speech-language	No	36 (39.1)	2 (40.0)	3 (21.4)	12 (70.6)	4 (100.)	5 (71.4)	24 (54.5)	3 (60.0)	9 (52.9)	5 (55.6)	5 (55.6)	14 (43.8)
	Yes	56 (60.9)	3 (60.0)	11 (78.6)	5 (24.4)	0 (0.0)	2 (28.6)	20 (45.5)	2 (40.0)	8 (47.1)	3 (44.4)	4 (44.4)	18 (56.2)
Early intervention	No	54 (58.7)	4 (80.0)	11 (78.6)	12 (70.6)	0 (0.0)	5 (71.4)	33 (75.0)	4 (80.0)	12 (70.6)	3 (37.5)	8 (88.9)	28 (87.5)
	Yes	38 (41.3)	1 (20.0)	3 (21.4)	5 (24.4)	4 (100.)	2 (28.6)	11 (25.0)	1 (20.0)	5 (29.4)	5 (62.5)	1 (11.1)	4 (12.5)
Physiotherapy	No	49 (45.8)	5 (100)	7 (50.0)	13 (76.5)	3 (75)	5 (71.4)	32 (72.7)	4 (80)	11 (64.7)	6 (75.0)	8 (88.9)	21 (65.6)
	Yes	51 (51,1)	0 (0.0)	7 (50.0)	4 (25.5)	1 (25)	2 (27.3)	129 (27.3)	1 (20)	6 (35,3)	2 (25)	1 (11.1)	11 (34.4)
Transportation	No	25 (27.2)	2 (40,0)	4 (28.6)	6 (35.3)	1 (25.0)	2 (28.6)	15 (34.1)	1 (20.0)	11 (64.7)	3 (37.5)	3 (33.3)	10 (31.3)
	Yes	67 (72.8)	3 (60.0)	10 (71.4)	11 (64.7)	3 (75.0)	5 (71.4)	29 (65.9)	4 (80.0)	6 (35.3)	5 (62.5)	6 (66.7)	22 (68.8)
Integrations	No	63 (68.5)	4 (80,0)	8 (57.1)	10 (58.8)	1 (25.0)	4 (57.1)	31 (70.5)	3 (60.0)	9 (52.9)	3 (37.5)	9 (100.0)	23 (71.9)
	Yes	29 (31.5)	1 (20.0)	6 (42.9)	7 (41.2)	3 (75.0)	3 (42.9)	13 (29.5)	2 (40.0)	8 (47.1)	5 (62.5)	0 (0.0)	9 (28.1)
Support	No	59 (64.1)	2 (40.0)	6 (42.9)	4 (23.5)	1 (25.0)	7 (57.1)	7 (15.9)	3 (60.0)	9 (52.9)	1 (12.5)	4 (44.4)	21 (65.6)
	Yes	33 (35.9)	3 (60,0)	8 (57.1)	13 (76.5)	3 (75.0)	37 (42.9)	37 (84.1)	2 (40.0)	8 (47.1)	7 (87.5)	5 (55.6)	11 (34.4)

Table 2: Correlation between service and disability: Rho (253) = 0.190, p=0.002

Service	Governorate	
	Phi	P
Diagnosis	0.226	0.227
Teaching	0.222	0.327
Rehabilitation	0.208	0.458
Institutionalization	0.338	0.005*
Courses	0.163	0.837
Physical Therapy	0,154	0.893
Speech Language	0.268	0.067*
Early Intervention	0.271	0.058
Physiotherapy	0.279	0.036*
Transportation	0.196	0.557
Integration	0,240	0.199
Support	0.401	0.000*

Results indicate that there was a significant correlation between service of institutionalization and the governorate in Jordan. That means the institutionalization service meet the needs of the individuals with disabilities in all governorate in Jordan (Phi =0.338. P= 0,005). Also there was a significant correlation between service of physiotherapy and governorate in Jordan which mean that physiotherapy services meet the needs of the individuals with disabilities in all governorate in Jordan (Ph=0.279, P=0.036)

Also there was a significant correlation between service of support and governorate in Jordan which mean that support services meet the needs of the individuals with disabilities in all governorates in Jordan (Ph=0.401, P=0.000).

6. Recommendation

Further studies were needed to be achieved to investigate the programmes related to each service and the quality of services delivered to individuals with disability in each center in Jordan.

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